

Copper-, Nickel- and Cobalt(II) Complexes of 1,4-Diamino-1,4-diaza-2,3-dioxobutane

K. C. SATPATHY^{a*}, A. K. PANDA^a, (MISS) A. NAYAK^a and S. CHINDA^b

^aP. G. Department of Chemistry, Sambalpur University, Jyoti Vihar-768 019

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Sonepur Collge, Sonepur Raj-767 017

Manuscript received 18 November 1991, revised 3 November 1992, accepted 13 April 1993

We have been interested in the synthesis of bioactive hydrazide complexes due to their biological activities¹ and other uses². In the present communication we describe some complexes of bivalent cobalt, nickel and copper with oxalic dihydrazide (1,4-diamino-1,4-diaza-2,3-dioxobutane) (DDDB).

Results and Discussion

All the complexes (Table 1) are highly coloured. They are quite stable under normal conditions and can be stored for a long time. The complexes have melting point above 250°. They are slightly soluble in cold water and hot ethanol and highly soluble in polar organic solvents such as dioxane. They are slowly attacked by acids. Addition of alkali intensifies the colour of the complexes. Molar conductance values (at room temperature) of the complexes suggest them to be electrolytes.

The ligand may be considered as consisting of amido-imido tautomers.

In the ir spectra, a broad multiplet spreading over 3 550–3 000 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to the combined mode of ν_{OH} , ν_{NH_2} and ν_{NH} . The broadness is due to strong hydrogen bonding³. The bands at ~ 1 665, ~ 1 640, ~ 1 610, ~ 1 420, ~ 1 255 and 1 120 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to δ_{NH_2} , $\nu_{C=O}$, $\nu_{C=N}$, ν_{C-O} , δ_{NH} and ρ_rNH_2 respectively. The lowering of normal $\nu_{C=O}$ is due to hydrogen bonding of carbonyl oxygen. These spectral data suggest the existence of the ligand in tautomeric forms along with hydrogen bonding.

The ir spectra of the complexes are complicated. The combined mode of ν_{OH} , ν_{NH_2} and ν_{NH} further broadens and loses its multiplet nature. The bands due to ν_{NH_2} and $\nu_{C=O}$ are unperturbed indicating their nonparticipation which is established by nonalteration of ν_{C-O} and ρ_rNH_2 . The ligand band due to $\nu_{C=N}$ and δ_{NH} undergo bathochromic shift in

the complexes with a strong band at ~ 1 585 cm⁻¹ and intense band ~ 1 250 cm⁻¹ respectively. This suggests participation of ligand through azomethine nitrogen and imido nitrogen. All the complexes show a band at ~ 365 cm⁻¹ assignable⁵ to ν_{M-N} . The cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes exhibit additional bands at ~ 730 and ~ 520 cm⁻¹ attributed to ρ_rH_2O and ρ_wH_2O for coordinated water⁶ supported by an additional band at ~ 340 cm⁻¹ attributed⁷ to ν_{M-O} .

In order to assign the nature of the anions (coordinated or free) the spectra of the nitrate complexes were studied. The coordination of NO_3^- is generally ascertained⁶ by the appearance of bands at ~ 1 200 and ~ 1 020 cm⁻¹ which are not observed in the ir spectra of the nitrate complexes suggesting the noncoordination of the anionic groups.

Since infrared spectra indicated the presence of coordinated water, thermal analysis was undertaken for the cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes. There was no weight-loss upto 120° indicating absence of lattice water⁸. The first weight-loss was encountered at 160° with an exothermic peak. The weight-loss corresponds to the loss of two molecules of water. Simultaneous removal of two molecules of water suggests that they are in the same chemical environment⁹.

Reflectance spectra of the cobalt(II) complexes show two bands around 8 800 and 19 100 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively. Band positions and magnetic moment values (4.85 B.M.) suggest a high-spin octahedral configuration for the cobalt(II) complexes with *Oh* symmetry.

The nickel(II) complexes show three bands at 11 200, 16 600 and 27 700 cm⁻¹ assignable to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transi-

tions respectively¹¹. The band positions and magnetic moment values (~2.98 B.M.) suggest a spin-free octahedral environment for the nickel(II) complexes having *Oh* symmetry.

the observed g_{\parallel} , g_{\perp} and A_{\parallel} values correspond to square-planar geometry of copper(II) complexes¹⁴. ($1-\alpha^2$) value for these complexes is 0.21. It indicates that the unpaired electron of copper(II) spends

TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA

Compd./ (Colour)	μ_{eff} B. M.	Analysis : Found/(Calcd.)				
		M	C	H	N*	X**
DDDB (White)			20.38 (20.33)	5.04 (5.08)	47.42 (47.45)	
[Cu(DDDB) ₂]Cl ₂ (Bright green)	1.81	17.08 (17.14)	12.98 (12.95)	3.22 (3.24)	30.19 (30.23)	19.08 (19.13)
[Cu(DDDB) ₂]Br ₂ (Deep green)	1.83	13.76 (13.83)	10.42 (10.45)	2.58 (2.63)	24.35 (24.38)	34.79 (34.77)
[Cu(DDDB) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ (Jade)	1.79	14.92 (14.99)	11.29 (11.33)	2.78 (2.85)	33.08 (33.05)	
[Cu(DDDB) ₂]SO ₄ (Corn flower)	1.86	16.02 (16.05)	12.08 (12.13)	3.02 (3.05)	28.36 (28.31)	8.03 (8.10)
[Ni(DDDB) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]Cl ₂ (Satin blue)	2.96	14.66 (14.61)	11.87 (11.95)	3.98 (4.01)	27.83 (27.88)	17.68 (17.64)
[Ni(DDDB) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]Br ₂ (Light blue)	2.99	11.98 (11.96)	9.75 (9.78)	3.26 (3.28)	22.78 (22.83)	32.59 (32.56)
[Ni(DDDB) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ (Porcelain)	3.02	12.88 (12.90)	10.53 (10.56)	3.52 (3.54)	30.81 (30.78)	
[Ni(DDDB) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]SO ₄ (Pale blue)	2.97	13.76 (13.74)	11.21 (11.25)	3.74 (3.77)	26.27 (26.24)	7.46 (7.50)
[Co(DDDB) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]Cl ₂ (Rose)	4.62	14.62 (14.65)	11.90 (11.94)	3.97 (4.01)	27.88 (27.87)	17.66 (17.63)
[Co(DDDB) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]Br ₂ (Rose)	4.53	11.94 (12.00)	9.72 (9.78)	3.25 (3.28)	22.80 (22.82)	32.58 (32.55)
[Co(DDDB) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ (Dawn pink)	4.56	12.88 (12.94)	10.51 (10.55)	3.45 (3.54)	30.80 (30.77)	
[Co(DDDB) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]SO ₄ (Pink)	4.52	13.74 (13.79)	11.21 (11.24)	3.72 (3.77)	26.24 (26.22)	7.48 (7.50)

*N includes nitrate nitrogen.

**X = Cl, Br or S.

The copper(II) complexes show a broad absorption band ~ 16 010 cm⁻¹ and the magnetic moment values (~ 1.82 B.M.) suggest a square-planar configuration¹² having *D*_{4h} symmetry.

The esr parameters for the copper(II) complexes are computed as follows : $g_{\parallel} = 2.27$, $g_{\perp} = 2.052$, $A_{\parallel} = -178.7 \times 10^{-4}$ cm⁻¹ and $A_{\perp} = -81.4 \times 10^4$ cm⁻¹. The covalency parameter α^2 is calculated from g_{\parallel} , g_{\perp} and a_{\parallel} values¹³ and found to be 0.79. The observed data show that g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} values are closure to 2 and $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp}$. This suggests major distortion in the copper(II) complex from *Oh* symmetry. Further,

about 21% of its time on the ligand nitrogen donor sites. The α^2 for these complex is nearly equal to Cu-N₄ systems like the copper(II) complexes with histidine and 2,2'-dipyridyl¹⁵.

The physicochemical studies of the complexes suggest square-planar stereochemistry around copper(II) while nickel(II) and cobalt(II) have octahedral geometry with water molecules occupying the *trans*-position.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR and G.R. grade. Solvents were used as such.

The ligand DDDDB was prepared following literature method¹⁶. To 80% hydrazinehydrate (30.4 ml, 0.4 mol) was added dropwise, diethyl oxalate (27 ml, 0.2 mol) when exothermic reaction took place. A white precipitate was formed immediately which was washed crystallised from rectified spirit.

All the complexes were prepared in an identical method as exemplified by the preparation of copper(II) complex. To DDDDB (1.18 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (25 ml), was added $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.85 g, 0.005 mol) and the mixture was refluxed for 2 h. A bright green coloured precipitate settled down upon cooling. It was washed with ethanol, dried in desiccator for 24 h and analysed.

Metal, halogen, nitrogen and sulphur contents were estimated by standard procedures, and carbon and hydrogen were estimated by semimicrocombustion method in a MLW microelementary CHN analyser. Molar conductance at room temperature was measured in 10^{-3} M dioxane solution using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge. Room temperature magnetic susceptibility measurements of solid samples were made by the Gouy method with $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{CNS})_4]$ as calibrant. The infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 398 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on a Carry-2390 spectrophotometer and esr spectra recorded as powder (polycrystalline) on an E-112 EPR spectrometer. Thermogravimetry investigation was made in the temperature range 20–700° in air at the rate of 10° per min. The molecular weight of the complexes were determined by Rast's method.

References

- ZH. V. MALODYKH, L. P. SYSOEVA and N. G. GAZETDINOVA, *Khim. Farm. Zh.*, 1980, **14**, 33; H. M. MOKHTAR, *Pharm. Zic.*, 1979, **34**, 150; G. T. BATTGER, *Agr. Bur. Entomol. Plant Quarantine US*, 1951, **15**, 17; K. TOKYOKOHO, *Phys. Chem. Res. Jpn.*, 1981, **128**, 702; T. M. AMINABHAVI, N. S. BIRADAR and W. E. RUDZINKI, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1983, **78**, 107.
- YU. P. KITAEV, B. I. BYZYKIN and T. V. TOEPOLSKAYA, *Russ. Chem. Rev.*, 1970, **39**, 441.
- C. N. R. RAO, "Chemical Application of Infrared Spectroscopy", Academic, New York, 1963.
- C. W. YOUNG and R. B. DUVAL, *Anal. Chem.*, 1951, **23**, 709; K. C. SATPATHY, A. K. PANDA, R. MISHRA, J. PRADHAN and A. P. CHOPDAR, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1989, **19**, 1051; K. C. SATPATHY, A. K. PANDA, R. MISHRA and I. PANDA, *Acta Chem. Hung.*, 1988, **125**, 529; K. NAKAMATO, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compound", 3rd. ed., Wiley, New York, 1978, p. 1978.
- L. E. GODYCHI and R. E. RUNDLE, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 1953, **6**, 487.
- K. NAKAMATO, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compound", 3rd. ed., Wiley, New York, 1978, p. 228.
- S. C. RAJ and B. SAHU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 46.
- P. R. SUKLA, V. A. SINGH and J. BHARGAV, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 620.
- B. SINGH, P. L. MAURYA, B. V. AGRAWAL and A. K. DEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 29.
- A. P. V. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, New York, 1968, p. 308.
- F. F. CURTIS, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1968, **3**, 3.
- M. R. MCWHINNIE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 2259.
- R. L. DUTTA and A. SYAMAL, "Elements of Magnetochemistry", S. Chand, New Delhi, 1982, p. 178.
- E. A. GOODMAN and J. B. RAYNOR, *Top. Inorg. Radiochem.*, 1970, **13**, 316.
- R. S. DRAGO, "Physical Methods in Inorganic Chemistry", Affiliated East-West, New Delhi, 1971, p. 355.
- R. J. W. CREMLYN and J. L. TURNER, *J. Chem. Soc. (C)*, 1970, 2629.

